

Influence of stress level and damage on sonic tomography imaging and on the estimation of deformability properties of historic stone masonry

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ABSTRACT

The paper evaluates the sensitivity of sonic tomography imaging of historic masonry structures to variations in stress level and damage. Six stone masonry walls with different geometries representative of historical typologies were constructed by a professional mason. A laboratory campaign was carried out, subjecting the walls to cyclic uniaxial compression tests. During the test, an automated sonic tomography system was used to inspect the wall under loading cycles of increasing amplitude, which led to obtain tomographic images during loading and compare them under different stress level and damage condition. The use of robotic systems was proved essential to carry out the sonic inspections simultaneously to the compression tests. Results show that sonic wave propagation is not only sensitive to damage level, but also to the stress state. Thus, sonic tomography has the potential to be used to measure damage and stress level of masonry components over time, for example during renovation works on an existing construction.

1. Introduction

One of the greatest challenges we face when we work with the masonry built heritage is that it is not obvious what is the condition within the existing structure. Nevertheless, we need to ensure its structural safety while acknowledging that ancient masonry buildings can be particularly vulnerable to certain actions, such as earthquake loading. As defined in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction [49], we need to invest in disaster risk reduction to strength the resilience of our cultural heritage. Consequently, to safeguard the architectural heritage, we need to make important decisions on structural retrofitting having limited information about the existing structure.

In this context, diagnostic studies gain much importance [24], as highlighted by ICOMOS [21]. The success of any structural retrofitting measure, which needs to comply with current intervention principles, such as minimum intervention and compatibility, will essentially depend on our ability to properly characterize the structure. We need to know the material properties, the geometry, construction details, loads acting on the structure and existing damage. Here, Non-Destructive Techniques (NDT) play a key role because they allow us to obtain

information without damaging the valuable fabric that needs to be preserved. However, since they started to be applied to assess existing masonry structures, which involve highly heterogeneous materials, the general understanding is that they are mostly helpful in a qualitative way [3,4,45,6,50].

Among the NDT that can be applied for masonry structures, those based on acoustic waves propagation are a typically preferred approach because there is scientific evidence of a correlation between the attributes related to the wave propagation throughout the masonry and its inner morphology or its material properties. For example, sonic tomography has been applied to evaluate the inner morphology of masonry elements [23,25,42,54,30], and sonic tests have been frequently used to obtain a preliminary estimation of the masonry elastic material properties [29,33,52,53,37].

The present work evaluates the potential of using sonic tomography to perform time-lapse tomography, i.e., to measure damage and stress level of stone masonry components over time. Recent works have shown the potential of time-lapse or 4-D tomographic imaging for other materials, e.g., rocks, based on non-destructive ultrasonic measurements [10,48,7]. They were able to detect the damage process associated with

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Fig. 1. Automated sonic tomography system: (back) Scanning laser vibrometer for reception; and (front) Cartesian robot for emission, including PC with control software.

the loading of rock materials, including the initiation and propagation of cracks and variation of mechanical properties. They used tomography as a full-field measurement technique to map the ultrasonic velocity in rock specimens over time, studying variations in mechanical properties and identifying crack localization zones. The studies found strong correlations between decreasing wave propagation velocity and damage, e.g. macroscopic strain and crack propagation [28].

Similarly, at the elasticity level, research has focused on using ultrasonic tomographic imaging to measure the stress level in rock samples subjected to compression [36]. Literature also reports that the acoustic wave velocity is highly stress-dependent in concrete specimens [20,46]. Typically, low stress levels close existing microcracks and results in an increase in wave velocities, i.e. acoustoelastic effect [5]. Acoustoelasticity and damage thus act simultaneously over the wave velocity and exert opposite effects on velocity variation, demanding more experimental investigations, particularly for more heterogeneous materials, such as masonry. Few works can be observed in the literature, but they confirm the sensitivity of acoustic waves to the stress state of the masonry [16].

The present research precisely aims to explore if such findings also apply to stone masonry, assessing the sensibility of using sonic tomography to damage and stress level. Literature has proven the value of sonic tomography for inspection, as a diagnosis procedure to evaluate the level of deterioration and damage at a specific time [23,54,51,30]. However, its use is typically hampered because of execution and processing issues. In particular, tomographic inspections are typically performed manually, consuming much time at operational level. The use of automated systems can help to overcome this limitation and also promote the use of tomography to measure stress level and damage over time, for example during renovation works on an existing construction, to assess specific masonry components that are considered more vulnerable.

For that purpose, the paper presents the results of a laboratory test campaign carried out, consisting of cyclic uniaxial compression strength tests performed on six stone masonry walls with different geometries (internal and external). During the tests, an automated sonic tomography system designed and fabricated by the authors [38] was used. The automation of the inspection allows to highly reduce the inspection time, obtaining tomographic images at different levels of loading. Mapping the spatial and temporal variations in sonic wave propagation velocity at different levels of axial loading can allow to obtain information on the damage process and stress level. Tomographic inspections are necessary for such investigations because historical masonry materials are discontinuous media in which the deformation can localize, so

that few measurements of sonic velocity across the sample are not sufficient and may overlook localized damage.

The paper firstly shows the sonic tomography instrumentation used, briefly describing the automated sonic tomography system designed by the research team. Then, the paper describes the laboratory test campaign, discussing the masonry specimens, test setup, instrumentation and loading history. The fourth section presents the results of the uniaxial compression tests. The fifth part discusses the sonic test results, focusing on the variation of sonic velocities at different loading levels (in terms of tomographic images and average velocities) and their comparison with the mechanical tests results. Finally, another important goal of the campaign was to obtain the deformability properties of the stone masonry walls, namely Young's modulus. The results of the uniaxial compression tests are compared with the ones obtained through NDT, aiming to validate the capabilities of sonic inspections to assess the masonry elastic properties.

2. Sonic tomography instrumentation

Inspection works of masonry heritage structures using NDT are typically carried out manually, which makes the process significantly time consuming. A tomographic inspection of a single cross-section of a portion of a masonry wall can take up to several hours. For the purpose of the present research, the inspections could not be carried out manually because: (a) the amount of time necessary to perform the inspection at each loading level would delay the experimental test beyond acceptable limits; and (b) under high compressive loading, the procedure could become dangerous for the operators. Thus, the goals of the present research could only be accomplished using an automated sonic tomography system, which was already developed by the authors and presented and described in detail in [38].

Briefly, the sonic emission system fabricated by the authors consists of a Cartesian robot that moves a hitting device throughout a work area of 0.9×0.5 m defined by a vertical frame. The hitting device is a movable metal slug attached to a spring inserted in a linear solenoid. The solenoid can be activated with the current, pulling the slug against the spring and then releasing it towards the surface under inspection. The hit generates the sonic wave. The robot can move the device in X, Y and Z directions, positioning it in the desired location. A scanning laser vibrometer (SLV) from Polytec (PSV-400) was used as the reception system. The SLV was placed on the opposite surface of the wall, receiving the sonic wave by pointing the laser beam in predefined locations (Fig. 1). The SLV records the time-history displacements of the point focused by the laser. Both systems are synchronized in time domain using a piezo-electric vibration sensor attached to the slug of the hitting device. The sensor is activated when the system hits the surface and triggers the recording of the signal by the LSV.

Control software was also previously developed by the authors, for the movement of the Cartesian robot and the activation and deactivation of the solenoid for hitting the surface and emit the sonic wave at a specific frequency and a specific number of times [31,38]. The SLV is controlled remotely by a second PC with its own commercial software, which is also automated. The vibration sensor used to synchronize both systems is connected to the SLV acquisition system, recording both emitted and recorded signal.

3. Laboratory campaign

The laboratory campaign consisted of cyclic uniaxial compression strength tests performed following the European Standard EN 1502-1 [8] to obtain the deformability properties, i.e., Young's modulus, and compressive of the different stone masonry types under evaluation. Besides the mechanical characterization of the masonry types, the primary aim of the study is to gather experimental data to assess the capabilities of sonic tomography to evaluate damage progression and stress level. The tests were carried out at the laboratory of the Eduardo

Fig. 2. Representative cross-sections (up) and elevations (bottom) of: (a) Wall 1; (b) Wall 2; (c) Wall 3; and (d) example of ashlar masonry wall (walls 4–6).

Torroja Institute for Construction Sciences (IETCC), from the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The present section describes the masonry specimens, the test set-up, loading protocol and instrumentation used for the uniaxial compression tests.

3.1. Masonry specimens

Six stone masonry walls were constructed at the Institute of Physical and Information Technologies (ITEFI) of CSIC. The walls were constructed by a professional stonemason and are representative of two common historical typologies: irregular masonry and ashlar masonry types. The type of stone used for building the walls is a limestone from north west of Spain, *Campaspero* stone, whose compressive strength is reported to be 136 MPa according to the manufacturer. The mortar is a low strength mortar made of traditional lime putty from Morón. The irregular masonry walls had overall dimensions of 60 cm × 40 cm × 90 cm (length x width x height) and had 5–6 rows (Fig. 2a). They are composed of 5–6 rough horizontal courses of varying height with non-parallelepiped stones of different sizes (average size is 0.16 m with 50% coefficient of variation). They are roughly composed of two leaves with an inner core of small dimensions and through-stones going through the whole width of the wall at some courses. The ashlar masonry walls were 70 cm × 50 cm × 70 cm and had four rows (Fig. 2b). Note that Fig. 2 also marks the location of the sections where tomographic inspections were carried out. The construction of the walls was carefully documented, generating detailed 3D photogrammetric models of each wall that include the position of each stone. The documentation process is carefully described in [38] and the resulting six models of each wall (walls and stones) are publicly available in an open repository [39].

Additionally, ultrasonic measurements were carried out in mortar specimens prepared during the construction and in each individual stone before being placed in the wall. Stones were also weighted and measured to estimate the density. The average longitudinal wave velocity (v_p) obtained for the stones is 4300 m/s and the transversal wave velocity (v_s) is 2600 m/s. Knowing the wave propagation velocity of longitudinal and transversal waves, as well as the density of the stones, the Poisson's ratio (ν) and dynamic modulus of elasticity (E_d) could be computed based on elastic wave theory and assuming an isotropic material, through the following expressions:

$$\nu = \frac{\left(\frac{v_p}{v_s}\right)^2 - 2}{2\left(\frac{v_p}{v_s}\right)^2 - 2} \quad (1)$$

$$v_p = \sqrt{\frac{E_d}{\rho} \frac{1 - \nu}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)}} \quad (2)$$

The resulting average dynamic modulus of elasticity calculated is 40 GPa. The average longitudinal and transversal wave velocities obtained for the mortar varied. Regarding the mortar used in irregular masonry walls, the average longitudinal wave velocity measured is approximately 2000 m/s and the transversal is approximately 1200 m/s, which results in an average modulus of elasticity of around 6 GPa. The average longitudinal wave velocity obtained for the mortar used in the ashlar masonry walls was 1250 m/s and the transversal is 800 m/s, which leads to an average modulus of elasticity of 2.7 GPa. The mortar specimens were also tested in compression, obtaining an average value of compressive strength of 2.1 MPa for the irregular masonry walls and 0.8 MPa for the ashlar masonry walls. A lower quality mortar was used by the stonemason to fill the thin joints of the ashlar masonry walls, ensuring their stability through a better workmanship. The density of stones and mortar was also calculated, resulting in average values of 2400 kg/m³ and 1750 kg/m³, respectively. After their construction, the walls were transported to the IETCC laboratory to carry out the mechanical characterization campaign.

3.2. Test setup and loading history

The uniaxial compression strength test was performed at the laboratory of the IETCC. Following indications of the European Standard EN1502-1 [8], the walls included at least one head joint and three masonry courses. The walls were leveled at the top with gypsum plaster. Then, a thick steel plate was located at the top to center and distribute evenly the compression load. Actuators with load capacity of 2500 kN and 10,000 kN were used for the irregular masonry walls and ashlar masonry walls, respectively. The deformation of the walls was recorded by means of four Linear Variable Displacement Transducer (LVDTs)

Fig. 3. Test setup: (a) wall front view where the Cartesian robot is located; (b) diagram with instrumentation and location.

Fig. 4. Loading protocol for: (a) irregular masonry walls; and (b) ashlar masonry walls.

placed on the longer sides of the walls, close to the edges (Fig. 3a). The reason behind the positioning of the LVDTs close to the edges was twofold: (a) to clear the central part of each side of the wall, allowing to place the Cartesian robot on one side; and (b) not to block the laser beam of the SLV that acquires the signal on the opposite surface. The vertical displacement of the masonry walls is later defined by averaging the displacements measured by the LVDTs. Fig. 3b shows a diagram with the setup of the tests carried out, which is also shown in Fig. 1.

The walls were subjected to cyclic compression under loading control. Based on the expected compressive strength, the loading history was designed to make cycles of progressively increasing loading in the pre-peak regime. Aiming to analyze the progression of damage from minor to moderate to heavy, the loading levels were initially decided as 25%, 50% and 75% of expected average compressive strength. After the cycles, the walls were tested until failure to have an estimation of the compressive strength of the walls. This value was also used to better adjust the cycles for the subsequent tests.

Fig. 4 shows a diagram with the loading protocol adopted for the tests. The loading rate considered follows the EN1502-1 [8], consisting of 0.15 N/mm²/min for the irregular masonry walls and 1.25 N/mm²/min for the ashlar masonry walls. Two cycles are performed for each loading level. After reaching the maximum load in each cycle, the load is sustained and a sonic tomography inspection is carried out. The sonic tomography inspections lasted an average of 30 min,

including 18 points of emission and 22 points of reception (as detailed in Section 5). An initial inspection was carried out before applying any load, obtaining an initial (t_0) tomographic image. Given the estimated compressive strength of each wall, the estimated duration of the full compression strength test was approximately 5 h for the irregular masonry walls ($f_{c,estimated} = 2$ MPa) and 6 h for the ashlar masonry walls ($f_{c,estimated} = 20$ MPa), including the six tomographic inspections (two per loading level).

4. Uniaxial compression stress results

The results shown in the present section include load-displacement curves and a discussion of the crack evolution and eventual collapse. Results were also used to estimate the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength of the masonry specimens. The raw data measured during the cyclic uniaxial compression tests has been uploaded in an open repository [40].

4.1. Load-displacement curves and damage evolution

Fig. 5 shows the average load-displacement curves for the three irregular masonry walls. Note that due to malfunction of instrumentation, displacement measurements of wall 3 could only be recorded after the descending branch of the third cycle. Fig. 6 shows the average load-

Fig. 5. Load-displacement curves for the three irregular masonry walls (1–3).

Fig. 6. Load-displacement curves for the three ashlar masonry walls (4–6).

Table 1
Maximum force and estimated compressive strength of the six masonry walls tested.

	Irregular walls				Ashlar walls			
	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Average (CoV)	Wall 4	Wall 5	Wall 6	Average (CoV)
F_{max} (kN)	516	710	579	602 (16%)	6222	6374	7896	6831 (13.5%)
f_c (MPa)	2.2	3.0	2.4	2.5 (16%)	17.8	18.2	22.6	19.5 (13.5%)

displacement curves for the three ashlar masonry walls. The curves only shown displacements until the end of the last cycle. After this, the LVDTs were removed from the wall and only the load was measured until

failure. Table 1 shows the maximum load reached during the six tests and the resulting estimated compressive strength.

Table 1 shows that the strength of the ashlar masonry walls is around

Fig. 7. Damage evolution during the tests for the three irregular masonry walls (1–3).

Fig. 8. Damage evolution during the tests for the three ashlar masonry walls (4–6).

Fig. 9. Example of estimation of Young’s modulus for: (a) wall 1 (irregular masonry); and (b) wall 4 (ashlar masonry).

Table 2
Estimated static Young’s modulus and E/f_c ratio obtained for the six masonry walls tested.

	Irregular walls				Ashlar walls			
	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Average (CoV)	Wall 4	Wall 5	Wall 6	Average (CoV)
E (GPa)	2.3	2.8	3.4	2.8 (20%)	12.4	11.1	11.5	11.6 (6%)
E/f_c (α)	1058	943	1418	1140 (22%)	695	607	511	604 (15%)

10 times higher than the irregular walls. Given that the materials applied are the same, results highlight the importance of the masonry arrangement in their mechanical properties. It should be noted that the values obtained exceed the typical values recommended in existing codes for both masonry typologies [13,35]. The ranges defined in the codes are 1.0–2.0 MPa and 5.8–8.2 MPa for the irregular masonry and ashlar masonry typologies, respectively.

Fig. 7 shows the damage evolution observed during the tests for the three irregular masonry walls. Cracking at the stone-mortar interfaces started for low levels of loading (e.g., Fig. 7a) and rapidly progressed with increasing loading. The first vertical cracks typically in the central area of the long sides of the wall and extend towards the corner as the compressive stress increased (e.g., Fig. 7b). It is noted for high levels of loading, stones also cracked (e.g., Fig. 7e). The common damage pattern consisted on an hourglass type failure in the long sides (e.g., Fig. 7c), together with the detachment of the two wall leaves, illustrated by the development of vertical crack in the middle of the short sides of the wall (e.g., Fig. 7g-i). Collapse typically occurred after local failure of one of the corners (e.g., Fig. 7f).

The damage evolution observed in the ashlar masonry walls was clearly different. Typically, no visible cracking was registered until exceeding 50–60% of the maximum load (e.g., Fig. 8a). A clear non-elastic behavior was observed during the application of the load in the first cycle (Fig. 6), which is associated to the crushing of the thin mortar bed joints. After the initial adjustment of the bed joints, the compressive behavior is determined by the limestone units. This is clearly illustrated by the cracking of the stones (e.g., Fig. 8g). Failing units typically shows parallel vertical cracks (e.g., Fig. 8b). In some cases, local failure of masonry units occurred at some corners (e.g., Fig. 8h), but it did not compromise the global behavior of the wall. In the end, the failure pattern observed did not differ significantly from the one observed for the irregular masonry walls. Vertical cracks appeared in the short sides, leading to the separation of the two leaves. Additionally, a partial hourglass type failure occurred in the long sides, but typically involving

only one corner leading to the failure of the specimen (e.g., Fig. 8c).

4.2. Estimation of modulus of elasticity

The static Young’s modulus (E) was estimated by fitting a straight line to the unloading/reloading branches of the stress-strain curves belonging to the first two loading levels, following recommendations by [19,43]. As shown in Fig. 9, four lines were fitted per test, corresponding to the first four cycles. The Young’s modulus was estimated by averaging the four values. Table 2 shows the results of the six tests with average values and the obtained E/f_c ratio (α). The E values obtained are again significantly above the range of typical values recommended in existing codes for both masonry typologies [13,35], which are 0.69–1.05 GPa and 2.4–3.3 GPa, for the irregular masonry and ashlar masonry typologies, respectively. This discrepancy may be attributed to the reported high compressive strength of the stone units (160 MPa). It is noted that the computed dynamic modulus of elasticity (E_d) of the stones (Section 3.1) is 40 GPa, while for the mortar, E_d varied, being 6 GPa and 2.7 GPa for the mortar used in the irregular and ashlar masonry walls, respectively.

With respect to α , standard codes assume values ranging between 550 [15] and 1000 [12]. Tomažević [47] proposes a range between 200 and 1000. The ratio obtained for the irregular masonry walls is slightly over the range proposed in the literature. The ratio obtained for the ashlar masonry walls lies well within the ranges proposed by the codes and close to the $\alpha = 550$, which is a common value recommended for historic masonry structures [1,37].

5. Sonic test results

Sonic tomographic inspections were carried out at the beginning of each test (no loading) and at peak load of each loading cycle, keeping the load constant during approximately 30 min to carry out each inspection. As shown in Fig. 3b, the tomographic inspection was carried out using

Fig. 10. Example of layout of emission (blue) and reception (red) points for the tomographic inspection of the irregular masonry walls, located on opposite surfaces of the wall (Wall 2).

Fig. 11. Example of layout of emission (blue) and reception (red) points for the tomographic inspection of the ashlar masonry walls, located on opposite surfaces of the wall (Wall 4).

the transmission method and the emission and reception are located in opposite sides of the walls. This configuration was preferred also to simulate real conditions of inspection in an existing building, where the short sides of the wall would not be accessible.

In the case of the irregular masonry ones, the location of inspection and reception points varied slightly according to morphology of the wall surface. Nevertheless, the layout was very similar in all of them, consisting of 4 rows (Fig. 10). For emission, the upper and bottom row had 3 points and the middle rows had 6 points each. For reception, the upper and bottom row had 4 points and the middle rows had also 7 points. In

the case of the ashlar masonry walls, the layout was the same in all of them, and is similar to the one described for the irregular masonry walls, including the 4 rows, one per horizontal course (Fig. 11).

The idea of reducing the number of points of the upper and bottom rows was to reduce the inspection time. Note that for each emission point, measurements were recorded in all 22 reception points. 10 hits were performed per reception point for later averaging, leading to a total of 220 hits (measurements) per emission point. The hitting frequency is three hits/s and, thus, the time of inspection per point is approximately 75 s. Since there are 18 emission points, the full tomographic inspection

Fig. 12. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 2 (irregular masonry wall) for increasing loading level. The location of the sections is marked in red in Fig. 2.

of a wall each time that the uniaxial compression test stopped took around 22 min. The goal was to keep the inspection time below 30 min. Thus, the focus was placed on inspecting the middle courses of the walls. The raw data collected is available in [41].

The post-processing of the collected data was also automated by developing specific software that is also published open source [32]. The full description of the methodology to do the automatic data processing and generate the tomographic image is provided in [38]. Essentially, the process consisted of: (a) noise elimination from emission and reception signal; (b) signal processing, filtering and averaging; and (c) automatic detection of wave arrival times. Note that, in the case of the irregular masonry walls, the averaging of the 10 signals per point was done during the post-processing, but for the ashlar masonry walls, the data was

averaged automatically during the collection by the SLV data acquisition system. The tomographic image was generated using the GeoTom CG software [17], which applies the Simultaneous Iterative Reconstructive Technique (SIRT) [22]. The method requires to specify the sonic ray paths, i.e. transmitter and receiver positions, and will assume that the transmission is straight between both points. The application of algebraic techniques are based on the estimation of the velocity spatial distribution within the cross-section, which is discretized it into a square grid of N cells. The travel time of the ray path is then estimated as a sum of the transition distance of the ray through each crossed cell divided by the velocity associated to each of these cells. Measurements of all the propagating ray paths from the transmitters to the receivers produce a system of equations with known values for the travel times and the

Fig. 13. Variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) within the cross-section at different heights of Wall 2 (irregular masonry wall) between consecutive loading levels (visible vertical cracks are marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth). The location of the sections is marked in red in Fig. 2.

lengths of the rays passing through the cells. The SIRT is the iterative method used to solve such system of equations until the error is below an expected threshold, but note that this is an ill posed problem with no unique solution requires.

The results obtained from the data processing included: (1) tomographic images of several cross-sections at the mid-height of each wall for different levels of loading; (2) sonic wave velocities between each emission and reception point for different levels of loading; and (3) estimation of the modulus of elasticity of the walls based on the computed sonic velocities. All the results are described in detail in the following subsections.

5.1. Variation of tomographic images for increasing loading levels

Sonic velocity tomographic images were generated at the peak of each cycle (F). Fig. 12 shows the variation of the tomographic images for increasing levels of load applied in the irregular masonry wall 2. The tomographic slices that are shown in each column correspond to cross-sections at different heights of the wall. Note that the three cross-sections correspond to the second, third and fourth course of Wall 2, whose elevation is shown in Fig. 10. The tomographic images are overlapped on the cross-sections of the walls extracted from the photogrammetric models [39]. The cross-section is approximate because: (a) the emission and reception points are not perfectly aligned

horizontally; and (b) the sonic transmission is not planar, as the sonic ray propagates in all directions. Thus, the cross-section is illustrative to better understand the interior morphology of the wall surrounding the area where the sonic wave is emitted and received.

The interpretation of the results is challenging because there is a high dispersion of measurement results caused by inhomogeneity of the material at all loading levels. Some aspects will be observed in all tomographic images generated due to the calculation process. For example, a X shape with lower velocity bands is common to many of the images. This is the result of several aspects. First, the travel times through the diagonal ray paths are typically higher (leading to lower velocities) because: (a) the sonic transmission between emission and reception in these cases is worse, as they had to go through several mortar joints and mortar-stone interfaces; (b) the signal is attenuated by the increased distance. Secondly, no emission or receiver was located at the short sides to better simulate real conditions of inspection in an existing building, where the short sides of the wall would not be accessible. As a result, there are fewer ray paths at the edges, which then have a heavier impact on the calculation. Since the transmission between points that are directly on opposite sides is typically better (better built edges with good contact between stones), the velocity distribution shows higher velocity values in the edges. To find convergence during the calculation, the solution tends to accumulate lower velocity values along the diagonals and higher ones at the edges.

Fig. 14. Vertical cracks at the short sides of wall 2 for the last cycle of increasing loading level: (a) left side; and (b) right side (according to the cross-sections shown in Fig. 13).

Even though further processing the tomographic images (e.g., removing outlying ray paths that are outside the common range of velocities of the rest of the cross-section) could help to remove the X shape visualization, the data was left unprocessed and all data (all ray paths) was used, not to distort the information. The tomographic images reflect the sonic transmission between points and do not aim to represent the exact inner morphology of the section (e.g., areas with low velocities do not reflect necessarily a void within the section). Moreover, results are more meaningful when analyzed by comparison. A significant decrease of the velocity at the edge for the last loading level with respect to the first loading level would reveal the probable occurrence of a vertical crack that separates both leaves, worsening the sonic transmission. This is the main objective of the paper, which is to see the influence of stress level and damage in the sonic velocities and tomographic images.

In this regard, the variation over time of the tomographic images of the three cross-sections is clear and shows the same trend (Fig. 12). Sonic velocities at the beginning of the test (when no load is applied) are low (<1000 m/s), typically higher at the edges (>3500 m/s), thus showing a good connection between the two leaves at the sides. The exception is the upper course ($h = 0.65$ m), whose left edge shows lower velocities, highlighting a worse transmission of sonic velocities and, thus, probably a worse connection between the two leaves. Nevertheless, the application of the first level of loading significantly increase the overall velocities within the cross-section. The compression of the wall (around 20% of the maximum compressive strength) highly improves the transmission of sonic waves, most likely because of a better (and direct) contact between the stones, closing possible micro cracking at the interfaces and minor inner voids. The improvement is again particularly evident in the cross-section of the fourth course (Fig. 12f). The previously loose connection of the left edge seems to be significantly improved, but also there is a better transmission (and higher velocities of 1000–1500 m/s) through the middle part of the cross-section. The

improvement of the sonic transmission through the middle part of the cross-section is common to the other two cross-sections. Note that the background color on the images corresponds to the average sonic velocity obtained per cross-section inspection during the compression tests.

To better understand the variation trends, Fig. 13a-c plots the variation of the sonic velocities (Δv_p) between the tomographic image corresponding to the first load increment and the initial tomographic image ($F = 0$ kN). The images highlight those areas where there is an improvement of the sonic transmission (in red) and, conversely, the areas where the sonic transmission worsens (in blue).

Fig. 13d-f plots the variations between the second loading level ($0.35F_{max}$) and the first one ($0.2F_{max}$) and Fig. 13g-i the variations between the third loading level (around $0.55F_{max}$) and the first one ($0.2F_{max}$). The variations observed after the first loading increment are not significant, obtaining very similar tomographic images. However, the application of the third loading level (around $0.55F_{max}$) caused a notable decrease of the sonic velocities. This is related to the significant cracking that could be observed for this loading level. The visible vertical cracks observed at the different loading stages are marked with a thick dotted black line for reference (note that the depth of the crack is unknown and thus is purely indicative) in Fig. 13. Cracks are widespread at the last loading stage. Two main vertical cracks running the whole height appeared at this loading level on the short sides (Fig. 14), revealing the separation of the two leaves. As a result, the tomographic images show a significant decrease of velocities at the edges. Note for example, how the velocities shown in the tomographic image of the cross-section at 0.5 m for the last loading level have significantly decreased on the right edge, probably due to the occurrence of the vertical crack that separates both leaves, worsening the sonic transmission. The left edge is less affected, which agrees with the damage observed at this side (Fig. 14a). Cracking is more widespread in the

Fig. 15. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 1 for increasing loading level (left); and variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) with visible vertical cracks marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth (right). The location of the sections is marked in red in Fig. 2.

upper courses, e.g., course 4 where a significant decrease of sonic transmission velocities can be indeed observed throughout the whole cross-section (Fig. 13i).

Because of the configuration of the sonic test, consisting of direct transmission between parallel sides, the cracks that run perpendicular to the transmission direction, e.g., the vertical cracks observed at the short sides, can be more easily identified and located looking at the variation of the sonic velocities. This is possible because these cracks directly hamper the transmission of sonic waves between the two leaves. Results thus show that the sonic velocities are sensitive to the stress level and damage.

Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 show the tomographic images at different loading levels of the other two irregular masonry walls: Wall 1 and Wall 3, respectively. The figures also show the variation of the sonic velocities (Δv_p) between different loading levels, with visible vertical cracks observed marked with a thick dotted black line for reference. The trend observed for both walls is very similar to the one previously described for Wall 2, consisting of a substantial increment of sonic wave velocities after the application of the first loading level (Fig. 15c-f) and then, a significant decrease after damage arise with high loading levels. Another clear example of this behavior can be seen with the cross-section of Wall 1, at $h = 0.55$ m. At this location, there is a through-stone and, as expected, results show that there is an overall good transmission of sonic waves because of its presence. After the application of the first loading level (Fig. 15e-f), the transmission highly improves throughout the whole section. At the last loading level ($F = 0.9F_{max}$), the transmission is

only good directly through the stone and at the two edges (Fig. 15m). Sonic velocities are low at both sides of the through-stone (<1000 m/s), which correspond well with the observed vertical cracks that arise surrounding the stone and propagate throughout the whole height of the wall (Fig. 7).

Results from the ashlar masonry walls (Wall 4–6) are shown in Figs. 17–19. Plots show the tomographic images at different loading levels and the variation of the sonic velocities (Δv_p), with visible vertical cracks observed marked with a thick dotted black line for reference. In general terms, the tomographic images obtained for the ashlar masonry walls show more homogeneous maps with higher velocities than those shown for the irregular masonry walls, since the beginning of the test ($F = 0$ kN). Fig. 17 shows the results for Wall 4. Overall velocities are increased when applying the first loading level (Fig. 17c-f). Particularly in the case of the upper cross-section ($h = 0.55$ m), which does not have an inner void, the map is almost homogeneous with velocities ranging between 2000 and 3000 m/s (Fig. 17e-f). Nevertheless, the velocities notably decrease with subsequent increments of loading level. At the second load step (approx. $0.7F_{max}$), the velocities are already reduced, particularly at the edges, which seems to be the results of the vertical cracks arising at the short sides of the wall, separating the two masonry leaves (Fig. 17g-j). At the last loading level ($F = 0.8F_{max}$), the velocities are highly reduced (Fig. 17k-n). The sonic transmission at the edges is notably worsened, which is in good agreement with the widespread damage and significant cracking observed for this loading level (Fig. 8).

The trend is similar for the other two ashlar masonry walls. In the

Fig. 16. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 3 for increasing loading level (left); and variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) with visible vertical cracks are marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth (right). The location of the sections is marked in red in Fig. 2.

case of Wall 5 (Fig. 18), the sonic transmission at the beginning of the test is poor, particularly at course 2, where there is a central core (Fig. 18a). This is probably due to the poor quality of the vertical mortar joints, possibly leading to lack of contact among stones and presence of voids. The contact between stones is gained after the application of the first level of loading, illustrated by the homogeneous sonic velocity maps shown in Fig. 18c and Fig. 18e. In the case of Wall 6, at the last loading stage, the highest variations are observed at the left side, showing an asymmetric decrease of the sonic velocities, which probably indicates that the separation between leaves arises first at this edge. The results thus show that the interpretation of the tomographic image also has the potential to help to locate damage.

5.2. Variation of sonic test average velocities with stress level

Results were also evaluated in terms of average sonic velocities measured during the uniaxial compressive strength test. As previously discussed, each emission point had 22 reception points. Since there were 18 emission points, a total of 396 sonic velocities were calculated per tomographic inspection carried out at the peak of each cycle. The increase or decrease in the average mean velocity can provide an overall idea of the internal condition of the wall at each stage.

Fig. 20 shows the variation of average sonic velocities during the test, for different stress levels (F/F_{max}), starting before the beginning of the test (no load). The graphs show the variation for each wall and the average (in dark red) for irregular masonry walls (Fig. 20a) and ashlar

masonry walls (Fig. 20b). Table 3 shows a summary of the average values and standard deviation calculated per wall and inspection cycle. Note that there was no cycle 6 for wall 4 because the wall was close to collapse after the application of the cycle 5.

The irregular masonry walls follow the trend observed in the tomographic images. The application of the first loading level (approx. $0.2-0.35F_{max}$) always results in a significant increment of the average sonic velocity. Overall, up to this first loading level, when there is no evident visible damage, we can expect an improved better transmission due to the improved contact between the stones, closing interfaces and minor inner voids. The velocity increases in average around 1.5 times with respect to the velocity corresponding to the unloaded stage. After this loading level, damage starts spreading. As a result, the simultaneous and opposite influence of damage and stress level on the sonic velocities makes the interpretation of the results challenging. With the exception of Wall 1, the sonic velocity starts decreasing when applying a loading level of approx. $0.5F_{max}$. The velocity then drops notably when applying a loading level over $0.75F_{max}$, when damage is severely widespread in all cases.

It should be also noted that the standard deviation (σ) is high in all inspections (Table 3), with values of Coefficient of Variation (CoV) close to 100% for the initial measurements to values leading to a 50% CoV for the rest of the cycles. Such values confirm the internal heterogeneity of the irregular masonry walls and indicate that a single measurement is not representative of the condition of a wall because damage is localized within the heterogeneous media. Moreover, the compressive loading

Fig. 17. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 4 for increasing loading level (left); and variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) with visible vertical cracks are marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth (right). The location of the sections is marked in red in Fig. 2.

applied is not uniformly distributed throughout the cross-section of the wall. As a result, the sonic transmission is also improved locally, at specific points, even for high levels of loading and damage.

The trend observed for the ashlar masonry walls barely differs. The sonic velocity boost after the application of the first loading level (approx. $0.2\text{--}0.35F_{max}$) is sharper, being almost 2.5 times higher in the case of wall 5 and around 1.7 times in average. The increment is due to the improved contact between stones. The weak thin mortar joints used for the construction crush for early loading stages and the sonic wave propagates directly through the stones. Particularly looking at the average curve in Fig. 20b, the results show a stepping decrease of sonic velocities per load step increment. After the second loading increment (approx. $0.5F_{max}$), the average velocity drops around 12% and then another 14% after the third loading increment (approx. $0.75F_{max}$). Besides the higher average velocity values in comparison with the irregular masonry walls, the standard deviation values are also lower. The CoV is around 50% for the initial measurements and around 30% for the other cycles. These values also highlight the significantly higher homogeneity of ashlar masonry walls.

5.3. Estimation of modulus of elasticity

The measurement of the velocities of sonic waves propagating through masonry has also been employed as a useful non-destructive method to obtain a preliminary estimation of its elastic properties, i.e., the modulus of elasticity. In the literature, the technique is referred as

sonic pulse velocity test or sonic tests [33,34,26,29,18]. The propagation of the mechanical energy generated by the hitting system through the material mainly consists of elastic waves [14]. As discussed in Section 3.1, the propagation velocity of these elastic waves (v_p) is correlated with the material properties, e.g., density (ρ), dynamic modulus of elasticity (E_d) and Poisson's ratio (ν) through the expressions from Eqs. (1) and (2).

Such expressions are included in several international standards for the inspection of concrete elements [2,9]. However, there are no standards for the use of sonic waves to estimate the mechanical properties of masonry material. The expression is developed for isotropic elastic materials and to standardize its use for masonry, more investigation is needed. The results of the present investigation also aims to explore the use of this expression for the estimation of the masonry properties, comparing the results with the modulus of elasticity (E) calculated by means of the uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) test (Section 4.2).

The expression shown in Eq. (2) was used to compute E_d . However, note that the sonic wave velocity used for the calculation of E_d was not the average wave velocity discussed in Section 5.2. The average velocity was computed using only the velocities between the upper and lower emission and reception layers, e.g., between emission points of row 1 (Figs. 10 and 11) and reception points of row 4, and vice versa, emission points of row 4 and reception points of row 1. These velocities are considered most representative of the sonic transmission in the vertical direction of the wall. Given the anisotropy of masonry, with varying material properties for different loading directions, the velocities

Fig. 18. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 5 for increasing loading level (left); and variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) with visible vertical cracks are marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth (right).

corresponding to the vertical loading direction are considered more appropriate to evaluate the vertical load bearing properties, e.g., the dynamic modulus of elasticity in the vertical direction. Table 4 shows the values of E_d computed based on the sonic velocities for all walls, at different loading levels. Note that a Poisson’s ratio of 0.25 and 0.2 was assumed for the irregular and ashlar masonry walls, respectively, and a density of 2000 kg/m^3 and 2300 kg/m^3 , based on common values from the literature.

The values are compared with the values of E calculated from the results of the UCS tests. An important aspect regarding the estimation of the modulus of elasticity using the sonic velocities is that the computed value corresponds to the dynamic modulus of elasticity and cannot be directly compared with the static modulus of elasticity obtained from the UCS [27]. This theoretical inequality that has no specific correlations for masonry has been studied in the present research by assessing the relationship between E_s from sonic velocities and E from UCS (E_d/E in Table 4).

The results are also shown graphically in Fig. 21, in terms of probabilistic logarithmic distributions, computed according to average values and the corresponding standard deviation (σ). The results highlight how E_d varies for different stress levels on the walls. Fig. 22 shows this variation in each wall and in terms of average values for each masonry typology. The trends shown in the graph are similar for both typologies.

The coefficient E_d/E also varies significantly according to stress level. When there is no loading, the coefficient is below 0.5 (0.28 in the case of the ashlar masonry walls). For the irregular masonry walls, the value increase up to 1.4 for the first loading level and decrease up to 1.2 and 1 for the subsequent increments of loading. In the case of the ashlar masonry walls, the coefficient increases up to 1 for the first increment and then decrease up to 0.84 for the last loading step. Some authors have proposed coefficients of 1.2 and 1.3 [11,44]. The present research indicates that this ratio depends on the stress level, as well as the masonry typology. Further research is needed to confirm this trend, but the results obtained suggest that the estimated load level on the masonry structure should be taken into account to compute the masonry modulus of elasticity.

6. Conclusions

The paper has focused on evaluating the influence of damage and stress level on the acoustic wave propagation within stone masonry, namely the sonic wave velocity. For that matter, an automated sonic tomography system was applied to perform tomographic inspections were carried out simultaneously to uniaxial compressive strength tests on six stone masonry walls with different geometries. The sonic wave propagation characteristics were thus evaluated at different stages of compressive stress loading.

Fig. 19. Variation of tomographic images in terms of velocities at different heights of Wall 6 for increasing loading level (left); and variation of sonic velocities (Δv_p) with visible vertical cracks are marked with a thick dotted black line and indicative depth (right).

Fig. 20. Variation of average sonic velocity measured for different stress levels: (a) irregular masonry walls; and (b) ashlar masonry walls.

The results illustrate that the sonic wave velocity and resulting tomographic imaging are sensitive to variations in stress level and damage. The application of compressive load (up to 20–30% of the

maximum strength), which does not cause any visible damage, results in a significant increment of the average sonic velocity. The increment is in average 1.5 and 1.7 times the sonic velocity of the unloaded specimen,

Table 3
Average sonic velocities obtained per wall and cycle and corresponding standard deviation (σ).

	Cycle 0		Cycle 1		Cycle 2		Cycle 3		Cycle 4		Cycle 5		Cycle 6		F/ F _{max}	
	v _{ave} (m/s)	σ (m/s)														
Irregular masonry walls	W1	1236	990	1904	1075	2059	1170	1980	1076	2129	1169	1439	850	1441	883	0.90
	W2	1117	1039	1425	835	1405	848	1490	799	1509	828	1307	714	1319	765	0.53
	W3	1059	813	1866	1024	1908	1005	1929	956	1579	715	1642	820	1762	1042	0.79
Ashlar masonry walls	Ave.	1137		1732		1791		1800		1739		1463		1507		0.74
	W4	1805	806	2504	745	2483	720	2205	616	2451	892	1949	571	1855	728	0.80
	W5	1263	866	3140	1084	2837	1027	2554	833	2481	883	1844	683	1855	728	0.75
	W6	2012	1080	2893	1030	2997	1123	2793	996	2693	1000	2608	1059	2568	994	0.60
Ave.	1693		2845		2772		2517		2542		2134		2211		0.70	

for the irregular and ashlar masonry walls, respectively. The better sonic transmission is the result of the improved contact between the stones, closing interfaces and minor inner voids. When damage arises, the simultaneous and opposite influence of damage and stress level on the sonic velocities complicates the interpretation of the results, which are more variable. Nevertheless, the sonic velocity invariably decreases notably when damage is severe, after applying a loading level of approx. 50% of the maximum strength. Tomographic imaging allows to observe the wave velocity distribution within the walls and potentially localize damage, but the interpretation of the results is difficult. The challenge is increased by the overall dispersion of measurement results caused by inhomogeneity of the material at all loading levels. However, areas where sonic transmission is hampered can be distinguished, which can be associated with damage. Future work needs to address improving the visualization of the results to better understand the inner condition of masonry structures to enhance interpretation.

Results show that measuring the sonic wave velocity can have the potential to evaluate stress level and damage on historic masonry walls for inspection and monitoring. Variations of the sonic velocity can be monitored along the service life of masonry structures, for example during renovation works on an existing construction, to evaluate stress level and detect and localize the occurrence of damage. Nevertheless, there is also a need of further investigation to achieve a reliable estimation of both variables. An important aspect would be the repetition of the test for lower loading levels and smaller increments (below 20% of the maximum strength, before damage arises), to better understand the independent influence of stress level in the sonic velocities.

The research has also explored the potential of using sonic wave velocities to estimate the masonry material properties, namely the modulus of elasticity. The results obtained demand further research to support the findings. The correlation between the dynamic modulus of elasticity computed from the sonic velocities and the static modulus of elasticity is not evident, but results show that it depends on the load level. Such dependence of the dynamic elastic modulus on the load level adds a difficulty on estimating the modulus of elasticity using sonic testing because it suggests that the stress level should be taken into consideration. Finally, it should be noted that the use of an automated system was essential to carry out the present study. In particular, for the estimation of the dynamic modulus of elasticity, a significant number of tests and averaging is necessary to avoid the effect of local features and defects.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

González Margarita: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anaya José Javier:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Meersman Marnix:** Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ortega Heras Javier:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Liébana Juan Carlos:** Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Aparicio Sofía:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper: The authors declare that they have no known financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests.

Table 4

Comparison between dynamic modulus of elasticity computed using sonic velocities (E_d) and values obtained from the uniaxial compressive strength tests, E .

		$F = 0 \text{ kN}$			$F = 0.25 F_{max}$			$F = 0.50 F_{max}$			$F = 0.75 F_{max}$			UCS	
		v_{ave} (m/s)	E_d (GPa)	E_d/E (-)	f_c (MPa)	E (GPa)									
Irregular masonry walls	W1	771	1.0	0.43	1576	4.1	1.78	1445	3.5	1.52	1098	2.0	0.87	516	2.3
	W2	1039	1.8	0.64	1455	3.5	1.25	1295	2.8	1.00	1428	3.4	1.21	710	2.8
	W3	825	1.1	0.32	1595	4.2	1.24	1475	3.6	1.06	1351	3.0	0.88	579	3.4
	Ave.	879	1.3	0.46	1542	4.0	1.41	1405	3.3	1.18	1293	2.8	1.00	602	2.8
	σ	142	0.4		138	0.7		162	0.7		158	0.7		99	0.6
Ashlar masonry walls	W4	1347	3.8	0.31	2217	10.2	0.82	2163	9.7	0.78	1905	7.5	0.60	6222	12.4
	W5	982	2.0	0.18	2570	13.7	1.23	2333	11.3	1.02	2065	8.8	0.79	6374	11.1
	W6	1390	4.0	0.35	2403	12.0	1.04	2401	11.9	1.03	2403	12.0	1.04	7896	11.5
	Ave.	1240	3.3	0.28	2396	11.9	1.02	2299	11.0	0.94	2168	9.8	0.84	6831	11.6
	σ	224	0.4		169	1.7		138	1.3		238	2.2		926	0.7

Fig. 21. Logarithmic probabilistic distribution of E , computed from average sonic velocities at different loading levels and obtained from UCS: (a) irregular masonry walls; (b) ashlar masonry walls.

Fig. 22. Variation of E_s for different stress levels: (a) irregular masonry walls; (b) ashlar masonry walls.

Data availability

I have shared link to data files in the paper.

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